

OQITIWSHINIŇ WAZIYPALARI

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ÓZMKÓMI NF “Folklor hám etnografiya” kafedrası

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***Annotaciya.** Bul maqalada oqıtıwshınıń qosıq sabaǵına tayarlıq kóriwi hám oqıtıwshınıń bir qatar wazıypaları berilgenligi haqqında sóz etilgen.*

***Gilt sózi:** Muzika, qosıq, nota, oqıw, sherek, jazba, awızsha, klass, muǵallım.*

TEACHER'S RESPONSIBILITIES

***Abstract.** This article describes the teacher's readiness for a spoon lesson and gives a number of teacher responsibilities.*

***Key word:** music, yalla, note, reading, quarter, written, oral, classroom, teacher.*

ОБЯЗАННОСТИ УЧИТЕЛЯ

***Аннотация.** В этой статье рассказывается о готовности учителя к уроку ложки и дается ряд обязанностей учителя.*

***Ключевое слово:** музыка, Ялла, нота, чтение, четверть, письменный, устный, класс, учитель.*

Muzika tárbiyasında jańa metodlardı islew, turmıs hám kórkem óner ortasındaǵı úziliksiz baylanıstı, muzika mádeniyatınıń mazmunı hám mánisin sáwlelendirip, túsindiriw maqsetinde anıq hádisler hám mısallardan paydalanıw zárúr.

Usı waqıyalardı ámelge asırıwda oqıtıwshı puxta tayarlıq kóriw, óz ústinde tınbay islewi, yaǵınıw bilim dárejesin, mádeniyatın, ilimiy ádebyatlar, jańa baǵdarlamalar, kórkem ádebiyatlar, teatr, muzeylerge barıp sanasın asırıw jolların rawajlandırıp barıw zárúr. Muzika sabaqları alıp barılatuǵın klass (auditoriya) úlgili bezetilgen bolıw kerek. Texnik quralları, metodik kórgizbeli qurallar, pianino, saz ásbapları (Qaraqalpaq, ózbek xalıq saz ásbapları) menen bezelgen bolıwı kerek. Solay etip qosıq sabaqların bárshe xızmetleriniń maqseti hám mazmunı sabaqtaǵı temalardı túsindirip, turmıs penen baylanıstırıp, sabaqtıń hámme bólimlerin bir biri menen úziliksiz alıp barıwdı talap etedi.

Qosıq sabaǵı basqa sabaqlardan óziniń kórkemliliǵı, qızıǵıwshılıǵı menen balalardı kóbirek emocional tuyǵılar hám obrazlı keshirmeler oyatıw menen ajralıp turadı. Sonıń ushın

qosıq sabađı eń áwele tárbiya sabađıdur. Qosıq sabqları tómendegi spetsipik qásietleri menen basqa sabaqlardan pariq qıladı.

1. Bul muzıka teoriyası hám atqarıwshılıđına tán túrli xızmetlerden: vokal-xor shınıđıwları, muzıka sawatı, muzıka tınlaw, balalarǵa saz ásbapların shertiwdi úyretiw, ritmik háreketlerdi bejeriw elementlerinen ibaratdur.

2. Muzıka basqa kórkem óner túrlerinen óziniń sáwlelendiriw quralları, yađınıy «tili» menen pariq qıladı.

Eger kórkem ádebiyat sóz benen, súwertlew óneri reńleri menen, oyın óneri háreketi menen sáwlelense, muzıka basqa, muzıkalıq seslerde payda bolǵan dawıs qurallarında sáwlelenedi. Joqarıda kórkem óner túrlerin kóriw hám esitiw arqalı qabil etsek, muzıkanı tek ǵana tınlaw arqalı ǵana qabil etemiz.

3. Muzıka anıq waqıt, ólshew menen baylanıslı kórkem óner. Sonıń ushın atqarılǵan muzıka tempine sazlanıp, onıń hár bir elementlerin dıqqat penen tınlamasań shıǵarmanı tolıq qabil ete almaysań.

4. Muzıka balalarǵa aktiv emocional tásir kórsetedi, quwandıradı hámde dóretiwshilktegi keshirmelerin oyatadı. Jaqsı mazmunlı, qızıqlı qosıq sabađı balalardıń sharshaǵanın shıǵarıp, kórkem mádeniy azıq aladı, shadlı, quwanışlı bolıp shıǵadı. Qullası, qosıq sabađı óziniń aktiv psixologik táhiri menen basqa pánlerden pariq qıladı.

Sonday-aq qosıq sabađı basqa pánler menen úzliksiz baylanısta. Súwretlew kórkem óneri, ádebiyat, ana-tili, tariyx, pedagogika, psixologiya, vokal, ritmika, anatomiya hám tađı basqalar. Bular qosıq sabađın turmıs penen baylanıstırıwǵa, mazmunlı, qızıqlı qılıp sabaq alıp barıwǵa járdem beredi. Qosıq sabađınıń dúzilisi úsh tiykarǵı xızmetten turadı: muzıka tınlaw, muzıka sawatı hám xor bolıp (birlikte) qosıq aytıwdan ibarat.

Tálimniń jańa modeli jámiyette ǵárezsiz pikirlewde erkin adamlardıń rawajlanıwına alıp keledi.

Mektep oqıwshılarınıń aldına qoyǵan maqsetleri:

1. Bilim (mámleketlik standart tiykarında).
2. Ǵárezsiz pikir júritiw.
3. Dúnyaga ilimiy kóz-qaras.
4. Ulıwma insanıylıq hám milily mádeniyat.
5. Dóretiwshilik.

Oqıwshılardıń jeke adamiylıq qásiyetleri:

1. Watanga muxabbat.

2. İnsaniylik.
3. Miynet súygishlik.
4. Sabır taqatlı, shıdamlılıq.
5. Erkin hám jańasha pikir júrgiziwshi qásiytlerge iye bolıw kerek.

Ózbekstan Respublikası ulıwma bilim beretuǵın mekteplerde muzıka bilim tárbiyasın konspektsiyasın hám mámleketlik standartın islep shıqtı. Sońǵı kúnlerde usı jańa baǵdarlama tiykarında mekteplerde sabaq ótiliw jolǵa qoyılǵan.

Búgingi kúnde muzikalıq tárbiyaǵa barlıq adamlardı muzikalıq iskusstvoǵa tartıp, sol arqalı hár tárepleme garmonikalıq rawajlanıwǵa múmkinshilik dúziw sıyaqlı talap qoyadı. Sonlıqtan ulıwma bilim beretuǵın mekteptiń oqıw planına muzıka páni kirgizilgen.

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